

The Impact of Salted Fish Business Management on Family Economic Improvement in Lemito District, Pohuwato Regency

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Abstract:- Lemito sub-district is one of 13 sub-districts in Pohuwato Regency, which stretches along the coast of Tomini Bay. In the Lemito area, most of the fishermen do salted fish preservation. However, the preservation is still traditional. Traditionally preserving salted fish aims to reduce the water content in the fish's body, so it does not provide an opportunity for bacteria to multiply. High-quality preservation results can be obtained with good treatment during the preservation process, such as maintaining the cleanliness of the materials and tools used, using fresh fish, and clean salt. Salted fish also has a higher protein content than fresh fish. To expedite the process salted fish management certainly requires the provision of a special place on the beach so that it can improve the family economy. Besides that, the community also needs capital assistance from both the government and financial institutions so that salted fish processors can improve their family's economy. This study aims to find out how to improve the management of the salted fish business and examine the effect of salted fish business management on increasing family economic income in Lemito Village, Lemito District, Pohuwato Regency, Gorontalo Province. This research is an explanatory research with a quantitative approach and uses a simple linear regression method. The population in this study were all fishery product processors in the salted fish production center business unit in Lemito Village, Lemito District, Pohuwato Regency, Gorontalo Province. Sampling using proportional random sampling technique. The data collection process uses questionnaires and tests (testing). The results of this study are expected to be able to confirm the findings to provide theoretical and practical contributions so that they can form the basis for efforts to increase the economic income of families engaged in salted fish production center businesses in Lemito Village, Lemito District, Pohuwato Regency, Gorontalo Province.

Keywords:- *Management of Salted Fish Business; Improvement of the Family Economy.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In Indonesia, salted fish is a well-known marine fishery product and is one of the processed fish products that is widely consumed by the public. This salted fish processing business is one of the efforts made by people on the coast to convert or process fresh marine fish into dried fish which is processed simply through a drying process with the help of sunlight. Apart from being affordable, this salted fish is also easy to

obtain and can improve the community's economy besides having a fairly high nutritional content (Sumantri et al 2020). The processing of salted fish is carried out to extend the shelf life and increase the selling value of the product. This preservation method is the easiest way to save fishermen's catches.

Based on the results of a survey in Lemito Village, most of the fishermen carry out preservation in a traditional way. Traditionally preserving fish aims to reduce the water content in the fish's body, so it does not provide an opportunity for bacteria to multiply. High-quality preservation results can be obtained with good treatment during the preservation process, such as maintaining the cleanliness of the materials and tools used, using fresh fish, and clean salt. Salted fish also has a higher protein content than fresh fish. According to Handajani (1994), the protein content of fresh fish per 100 grams is 17% while the protein content of salted fish is 1.50% lower than that of fresh fish which is 4.50%. This makes salted fish more beneficial in terms of health.

To expedite the process of managing salted fish, of course, it is necessary to provide a special place on the beach for the management of salted fish business. With the availability of a special place to manage this salted fish business, it can certainly improve the family economy in Lemito District. This is in line with Pamudji's opinion (2009: 36) regarding management which focuses on two important factors, namely: a). Management as development that changes something so that it becomes new and has a higher value; and b). Management as renewal is the effort to maintain something so that it is better suited to needs. For people who rely on salted fish business as a necessity of life, especially in Lemito Village, Lemito District, Pohuwato Regency, around 30% who have a livelihood producing salted fish certainly really hope for the existence of this location. Likewise, the marketing system in Lemito Village, Lemito District, is not very good. Due to the absence of a market that sells salted fish specifically, the sales system still depends on information from people who go on and on. The lack of use of information systems through the media so that sometimes they only rely on sales through acquaintances or relations through relatives. Due to the absence of a market that sells salted fish specifically, the sales system still depends on information from people who go on and on. The lack of use of information systems through the media so that sometimes they only rely on sales through acquaintances or relations through relatives. Due to the absence of a market that sells salted fish specifically, the sales system still depends on information from people who go on

and on. The lack of use of information systems through the media so that sometimes they only rely on sales through acquaintances or relations through relatives.

On the other hand price is an important thing that must be considered because prices can affect the level of salted fish production which can result in high and low family economic income. The high or low prices can be influenced by certain factors such as low levels of public consumption of salted fish, and the weather that hampers the management of salted fish business activities, as well as the quality of salted fish. However, in reality what happened in Lemito village, the planning, implementation and results have not gone well, resulting in low family economic income.

Besides that, the fact that has developed to date, the support from the community, government agencies, and related parties is still not fully in terms of empowering and increasing family economic income for salted fish entrepreneurs. This is further strengthened by the recognition that their business capital is also their own capital and does not come from a financial institution, this is based on the results of a survey of salted fish processors in Lemito Village, Lemito District, Pohuwato Regency. To be able to improve the family economy, the people of Lemito Village, Lemito District, Pohuwato Regency must be able to play an active role in carrying out effective ways that can encourage economic growth, for example by managing natural resources (fish) properly and innovating both in terms of preserving salted fish and in marketing the product.

II. METHOD

In improving the family economy, especially this research is a type of associative research with a quantitative approach which aims to examine the influence between variables, namely the effect of business management (X) on increasing family economic income (Y). In Lemito Village, Lemito District, Pohuwato Regency, Gorontalo Province. The research instrument used was a questionnaire. The population in this study are all business centers processors of fishery products in processed fish production centers in Lemito Village, Lemito District, totaling 40 business units and all of them were used as samples in this study. The data analysis technique used in this study is a simple linear regression analysis technique using the IBM statistics SPSS software application version 21.0.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the research objectives that have been stated previously, the results that have been achieved in this study are the results of testing in each research stage and the answers to the research objectives and hypotheses.

➤ *Description of Business Management Variable Data*

Work environment variable data obtained from the results of the distribution of questionnaires. The number of question items in the questionnaire to determine the condition of business management variables consists of 15 questions with a maximum weight of 5 and a minimum of 1. A total of 40

business unit centers are the sample in this study. Based on the business management variable data (X) the diagram can be presented as follows:

Fig 1: Distribution Diagram of Business Management Variables

Based on the diagram above, it can be seen that in general, respondents who are business owners of fish processing centers provide the most choices in the category of strongly agreeing to business management variables. This can be interpreted that in general the variables of business management are in the high category.

➤ *Variable Data Description of Family Economic Income Increase*

Variable data on increasing family economic income were obtained from the results of the questionnaire distribution. The number of question items in the questionnaire to determine the variable condition of increasing family economic income consists of 15 questions with a maximum weight of 5 and a minimum of 1. A total of 40 business unit centers are samples in this study. Based on the variable data of increasing family economic income (Y), the diagram can be presented as follows:

Fig 2: Distribution Diagram of the Variable Increase in Family Economic Income.

Based on the diagram above, it can be seen that in general, respondents who are business owners of fish processing centers provide the most choices in the category of strongly agreeing

to the variable of increasing family economic income. This can be interpreted that in general the family economic income variable is in the high category.

➤ *Business Management Variable Validity*

Table 1: Business Management Variable Validity

Item No	r count	r table 5% df = (N-2)	Sig.	Criteria
1	0.426	0.312	0.006	Valid
2	0.686	0.312	0.000	Valid
3	0.738	0.312	0.000	Valid
4	0.674	0.312	0.000	Valid
5	0.563	0.312	0.000	Valid
6	0.459	0.312	0.003	Valid
7	0.574	0.312	0.000	Valid
8	0.617	0.312	0.000	Valid
9	0.554	0.312	0.000	Valid
10	0.696	0.312	0.000	Valid
11	0.631	0.312	0.000	Valid
12	0.811	0.312	0.000	Valid
13	0.736	0.312	0.000	Valid
14	0.742	0.312	0.000	Valid
15	0.766	0.312	0.000	Valid

➤ *Increasing Family Economic Income Variable Validity*

Table 2: Increasing Family Economic Income Variable Validity

Item No	r count	r table 5% df = (N-2)	Sig.	Criteria
1	0.659	0.312	0.000	Valid
2	0.824	0.312	0.000	Valid
3	0.791	0.312	0.000	Valid
4	0.832	0.312	0.000	Valid
5	0.650	0.312	0.000	Valid
6	0.905	0.312	0.000	Valid
7	0.773	0.312	0.000	Valid
8	0.788	0.312	0.000	Valid
9	0.856	0.312	0.000	Valid
10	0.799	0.312	0.000	Valid
11	0.808	0.312	0.000	Valid
12	0.799	0.312	0.000	Valid
13	0.832	0.312	0.000	Valid
14	0.840	0.312	0.000	Valid
15	0.724	0.312	0.000	Valid

➤ *Instrument Reliability*

Table 3: Instrument Reliability

No	Variable	Cronbach Alpha	Rtable	Information
1.	Work environment	0.896	0.600	Reliable
2.	employee performance	0.956	0.600	Reliable

Based on the data from the results of testing the validity and reliability of the instruments in the table above, it can be seen that all question items for each variable are declared valid and reliable so that they are feasible and can be used for research.

➤ *Data Normality Test*

Table 4: Normality Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residuals
N		40
Normal Parameters, b	Means	,0000000
	std. Deviation	4.05005347
Most Extreme Differences	absolute	,120
	Positive	,120
	Negative	-.098
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		,761
asympt. Sig. (2-tailed)		,609
a. Test distribution is Normal.		
b. Calculated from data.		

➤ *Data Heteroscedasticity Test*

Fig 3: Scatterplot

Based on the data from the prerequisite analysis test results in the tables and figures above, it can be seen and concluded that the research data to be used fulfills the normality and heteroscedasticity testing requirements so that it can be continued for testing the research hypothesis.

➤ *Regression Analysis*

Analysis Regression is used to see the effect of the independent (independent) variable on the dependent (dependent) variable and to predict the dependent (dependent)

variable using the independent (independent) variable. The results of the analysis using the help of the IBM SPSS Statistics version 21.0 program. displayed as follows:

Table 5: Regression Analysis Results (a)

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	13,814	7,443		1,856	,071
	Management Business	,806	,112	,758	7,173	,000
a. Dependent Variable: Family Economy Increase Revenue						

Based on the results of the analysis above, the simple linear regression model built is:

$$\hat{Y} = 13.814 + 0.806X$$

From this model it is interpreted as follows:

- a. If there is no influence from the business management variable (the effect is not significant), then the average increase in family economic income is 13,814 units.
- b. Every change in business management variables will affect the increase in family economic income by 0.806 times the unit.
- c. There is an influence of business management on increasing family economic income.

After obtaining the estimated regression equation model, the next step is to test the hypothesis. Testing is done using the t test.

The statistical hypothesis to be tested is as follows:

H₀: β = 0 meaning there is no effect variable X (business management) to variable Y (increase in family economic income).

H₁: β ≠ 0 meaning that there is an influence of variable X (business management) on variable Y (increasing family economic income).

The test criterion is that if the value is ≥ , then it is rejected, it is accepted, it means it is significant. If the value ≤ , then accepted and rejected means not significant. By using the help of the SPSS 17 for windows program, the following results are obtained;

Table 6: Regression Analysis Results (b)

Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	13,814	7,443		1,856	,071
	Management Business	,806	,112	,758	7,173	,000
a. Dependent Variable: Family Economy Increase Revenue						

From the results above, a value of 7,173 is obtained and a significant level is 0.001. Thus the significant test results are obtained as follows;

Table 7: Significant Test Result

Significance Level α	Score <i>t_{hitung}</i>	Score <i>t_{tabel}</i>	Significance Value	Conclusion
5%	7.173	2,021	0.000	Significant

Based on the significant test results, it is obtained that the value is > at the α significance level of 5%, then rejected is accepted, meaning it is significant. This gives an indication that business management affects the increase in family economic income.

➤ *Correlation Analysis*

To determine the magnitude of the closeness of the relationship between the work environment (X) and employee performance variables (Y) the Pearson correlation coefficient is used. By using the help of the IBM Statistics SPSS version 21.0 program, the correlation coefficient values are obtained as follows:

Table 8: Summary model b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	std. Error of the Estimate
1	,758a	,575	,564	4.10300

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Business_Management
- b. Dependent Variable: Family_Economy_Increase_Revenue

Based on the results of the analysis above, the value of the Pearson correlation coefficient is 0.758. This shows that there is a strong relationship between business management (X) and family economic income (Y).in Salted Fish Management Business in Lemito Village, Lemito District, Pohuwato Regency, Gorontalo Province.

➤ Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

The coefficient of determination reflects the magnitude of the influence of changes in the independent variables in carrying out changes to the dependent variable together, with the aim of measuring the correctness and goodness of the relationship between variables in the model used. The value ranges from $0 << 1$. If the value gets closer to one then the proposed model is said to be good because the higher the variation in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variable. Based on the estimation results of the regression equation model that has been carried out above, the determinant coefficient values are obtained as follows:

Table 9: Coefficient of Determination of X against Y

R	RSquare	Contribution of Other Factors
0.758	0.575	0.425

Based on the results above, an R-Square of 0.575 is obtained. This value means that 57.5% of the variability regarding the increase in family economic income in Salted Fish Management Business in Lemito Village, Lemito District, Pohuwato Regency, Gorontalo Province can be explained by business management, while the remaining 42.5% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

The findings and results of this study are in line with research conducted by Mei Rani Amelia (2018) with the results of the research which stated that the way business management affects the income of micro, small and medium enterprises in the case study of MSMEs in Batik Bengkel Village, Tegal Regency. Then research conducted by Ay Ling (2013) on business development and management in small micro and medium enterprises with the results of research that business management includes management of the internal business environment is a determinant of business success and business income. Furthermore, the results of research conducted by Eva Riani (2014); Fauzan Hakiki (2020); with the results of the study that the factors that influence the income of small businesses include how the business is managed by the business owner.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results described above, it can be concluded that 57.5% variability regarding the increase in family economic income in Salted Fish Management Business in Lemito Village, Lemito District, Pohuwato Regency, Gorontalo Province can be explained by business management, while the remaining 42.5% is influenced by other variables not examined in this study. PTests on research variables which include business management and increasing family economic income have been carried out and have answered the research objectives and research hypotheses.

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